

THE INFLUENCE OF HUMAN RESOURCES AND ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE ON THE QUALITY OF ONE-DOOR INTEGRATED SERVICES AT THE BANDUNG HIGH COURT THROUGH JOB SATISFACTION AS A MEDIATION VARIABLE

Budyawan Herijanto¹, Vip Paramarta², Kosasih³, Farida Yuliaty⁴, Y. Ony Djogo⁵, Fitriana⁶.

Program Studi Magister Manajemen, Universitas Sangga Buana YPKP, Bandung

E-mail: Budy86.southline@gmail.com¹, vip@usbypkp.ac.id², kosasih@usbypkp.ac.id³,
farida.yuliaty@usbypkp.ac.id⁴, ony.djogo@usbypkp.ac.id⁵,
fitriana@usbypkp.ac.id⁶

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the mediating role of job satisfaction in the influence of human resources (HR) and organizational culture on the quality of the One-Stop Integrated Service (PTSP) at the Bandung High Court. The background of this study is the persistence of public complaints regarding aspects of service speed and procedures, which indicates the need to strengthen internal organizational factors. This study uses a quantitative approach with an explanatory method. The research sample consisted of 103 employees determined using the Slovin formula from a total population of 137 people. Data were analyzed using path analysis with the help of IBM SPSS version 26. The results showed that HR and organizational culture have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction and service quality. Job satisfaction was proven to have a significant effect on service quality. However, the Sobel test showed that job satisfaction does not act as a significant mediator in the relationship between HR and organizational culture on service quality. Organizational culture has a more dominant influence than HR. This finding confirms that improving service quality in judicial institutions is more effective if it is focused on directly strengthening HR and organizational culture, in addition to efforts to improve employee job satisfaction.

Keywords: *organizational culture; job satisfaction; service quality; PTSP; human resources*

INTRODUCTION

Bureaucratic reform and strengthening public services are the main focus of the Indonesian government in improving the quality of government services, including in the judicial environment. (Zahwa Alia Putri et al., 2025) One concrete manifestation of this reform is the implementation of the One-Stop Integrated Service System (PTSP), which aims to provide convenience, speed, and transparency in the provision of services to the public. (Erlinda, 2025). PTSP in the judicial environment is designed to unify various service processes in one door so that the public does not have to deal with many units, thereby increasing efficiency and convenience. (Yani et al., 2024). The Bandung High Court, as one of the institutions administering the One-Stop Integrated Service (PTSP), plays a strategic role in achieving excellent service. However, a pre-survey of 25 respondents indicated a gap between expectations and the reality of service delivery. The main issues identified were service speed, which 52% of respondents rated as poor, and accuracy and transparency, which also received low ratings. These findings indicate the need for further attention to internal organizational factors that influence service quality. The success of service innovations such as PTSP is greatly influenced by the quality of human resources (HR) and organizational culture. (Ilhami et al., 2024). Highly qualified, competent human resources with a high service orientation are the main key to ensuring that innovation implementation runs effectively. (Alivia & Raharjo, 2024) However, the pre-survey indicated that the effectiveness of ongoing training remains a major issue, with 48% of respondents rating it as inadequate, followed by work motivation, which also needs improvement. Furthermore, a conducive organizational culture aligned with public service principles also plays a crucial role. The pre-survey results showed that the service orientation dimension received the lowest score, indicating a still weak collective commitment to implementing the principle of excellent service. (Guruh Suksmono Aji & Iva Khoiril Mala, 2024). Job satisfaction is

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an important factor that bridges the influence between HR management and organizational culture on improving employee performance.(Wahyutomo & Zikri, 2024)When employees feel valued and comfortable, they are intrinsically motivated to perform optimally. Pre-survey results indicate that while working relationships and supervisory supervision are considered good, underlying employee dissatisfaction stems from perceived inadequate compensation systems and promotion opportunities. This can impact employee morale and commitment to providing excellent service.

Research on the influence of human resources and organizational culture on service quality, with job satisfaction as a mediating variable in the judicial environment, is still limited. Several previous studies have examined the relationship between these variables separately in different sectors. Research by(Emria & Nurhidayati, 2025)in hospitals found that service quality mediated the relationship between HR competency and organizational culture on employee performance. Meanwhile,(Wahyutomo & Zikri, 2024)Research in the banking sector shows that organizational culture significantly influences job satisfaction and service quality. However, a comprehensive mediation model in judicial institutions, particularly in the PTSP unit, has not been widely explored. This study aims to fill this gap by analyzing the role of job satisfaction in mediating the influence of human resources and organizational culture on PTSP service quality at the Bandung High Court.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Human Resources (HR)

Human Resources (HR) are a key strategic asset that determines an organization's success and competitive advantage. Robbins & Judge (2019) state that quality HR is characterized by relevant competencies, adequate experience, and the ability to adapt to change. In the context of public service, HR is viewed as individuals who possess the knowledge, skills, and potential to contribute to achieving organizational goals.(Shopiana, 2021). The HR components in this study include competency, work motivation, ongoing training, and career development, which are rooted in Human Capital theory and Motivation-Hygiene theory.(Esisuarni et al., 2024; Wirawan et al., 2025)

Organizational culture

Organizational culture is a system of values, norms, habits and behavioral patterns that are inherent in the members of an organization and collectively form the identity and character of the organization.(El-sayed et al., 2021)A positive and adaptive organizational culture will align with the organization's strategic goals, improving employee performance and satisfaction.(Ghaleb, 2024)In the context of bureaucratic reform, an adaptive and innovative organizational culture is a determining factor in the successful implementation of a modern service system such as PTSP.(Taufiqurrohman Syahuri & M. Reza Saputra, 2024)The components of organizational culture in this study are the values of diversity and innovation, service orientation, work ethics and integrity, and employee involvement.(Erlinda, 2025; Firlana, 2025).

Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is an emotional condition experienced by an individual in assessing his/her work, whether in the form of pleasant or unpleasant feelings.(Hendri Gusma Hendra et al., 2024). Job satisfaction reflects a positive attitude toward work that arises from an individual's evaluation of the characteristics of his or her job.(Mukmin & Prasetyo, 2021)A satisfied person tends to demonstrate higher levels of commitment and loyalty. The components of job satisfaction in this study include compensation, supervision, the work itself, relationships with coworkers, working conditions, promotion opportunities, and job security.(Feri et al., 2020; Medah et al., 2024).

Quality of Service

Service quality is a key indicator in assessing the success and effectiveness of public organizations. According to Parasuraman's 1988 SERVQUAL model, service quality is measured through the dimensions of tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. In the context of PTSP in judicial institutions, service quality is measured not only by administrative speed and efficiency, but also by transparency, fairness, and professionalism of officers.(Mokoginta et al., 2023; Yani et al., 2024). The service quality components in this study include service speed, accuracy and transparency, officer responsiveness, friendly and professional attitude, and fairness in the service process.

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Relationship between Variables and Hypothesis Development

Previous research shows that the quality of human resources has a positive and significant influence on the quality of public services.(Lufitasari et al., 2023; Sahriani et al., 2022)Competent human resources are able to provide responsive, accurate, and satisfactory services. Similarly, organizational culture has been shown to have a positive and significant influence on service quality.(Rusdi, 2023; Tui et al., 2024)Strong cultural values create a conducive work environment that encourages employees to provide the best service. The quality of human resources and organizational culture also influence job satisfaction. Research by(Susanti et al., 2023)shows that the quality of human resources has a positive effect on employee performance, which is correlated with job satisfaction. Meanwhile,(Wahyutomo & Zikri, 2024)confirms that organizational culture has a significant influence on job satisfaction. High job satisfaction, in turn, will encourage employees to provide better service.(Syahputra et al., 2023).

Furthermore, job satisfaction is positioned as a mediating variable. Research by(Emria & Nurhidayati, 2025)The results show that service quality mediates the relationship between HR competency and organizational culture on employee performance. This indicates that HR and organizational culture not only directly influence service quality but also through improving employee psychological well-being, such as job satisfaction. Based on these theoretical and empirical studies, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H1: HR has a positive influence on job satisfaction;

H2: Organizational culture has a positive effect on job satisfaction;

H3: HR has a positive influence on service quality;

H4: Organizational culture has a positive influence on service quality;

H5: Job satisfaction has a positive effect on service quality;

H6: Human resources and organizational culture have a simultaneous influence on job satisfaction;

H7: Job satisfaction mediates the influence of HR on service quality;

H8: Job satisfaction mediates the influence of organizational culture on service quality.

METHOD

This study employed a quantitative approach with an explanatory method. The research location was the Bandung High Court. The population in this study was all employees involved in the PTSP service, totaling 137 people. The sample was determined using the Slovin formula with a 5% error rate, resulting in a sample size of 103 respondents. The sampling technique used purposive sampling with the criteria of employees having at least one year of experience in public service within the court environment. Data were collected through a questionnaire compiled based on research variable indicators with a Likert scale of 1–5. The research instrument was tested for validity using Pearson Product Moment correlation and reliability using Cronbach's Alpha. The data analysis technique used was path analysis with the help of IBM SPSS version 26. Prior to the path analysis, classical assumption tests were conducted, including tests for normality, heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity, and autocorrelation. To test the significance of the mediation effect, the Sobel test was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research result

Respondent Characteristics

Table 1. Respondent Characteristics

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Man	50	48.54
Woman	53	51.46
Age		
27–30 years old	25	24.27
31–40 years	35	33.98
41–50 years	30	29.13
> 50 years	13	12.62
Last education		
High School/Vocational School	36	34.95
Bachelor degree)	67	65.05

Source: Data Processed by Researchers, 2025 (SPSS 26)

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Table 1 shows that the number of respondents in the study was 103, consisting of 48.54% male and 51.46% female. The majority of respondents were in the productive age group of 31–40 years (33.98%) and 41–50 years (29.13%). In terms of education, 65.05% of respondents were bachelor's degree graduates (S1), and 34.95% were high school/vocational school graduates.

Data Validity Test

Table 2. Validity Test

Variables	Item	Validity			Reliability		
		Validity Coefficient	Critical Point	Valid	Reliability Coefficient	Critical Point	Reliable
HR (X1)	1	0.892	0.3610	Valid	0.888	0.700	Reliable
	2	0.914	0.3610	Valid			
	3	0.819	0.3610	Valid			
	4	0.852	0.3610	Valid			
Organizational Culture (X2)	1	0.826	0.3610	Valid	0.851	0.700	Reliable
	2	0.894	0.3610	Valid			
	3	0.864	0.3610	Valid			
	4	0.776	0.3610	Valid			
Quality of Service (Y)	1	0.785	0.3610	Valid	0.837	0.700	Reliable
	2	0.377	0.3610	Valid			
	3	0.714	0.3610	Valid			
	4	0.777	0.3610	Valid			
	5	0.722	0.3610	Valid			
	6	0.762	0.3610	Valid			
	7	0.844	0.3610	Valid			
Job Satisfaction (Z)	1	0.869	0.3610	Valid	0.925	0.700	Reliable
	2	0.875	0.3610	Valid			
	3	0.850	0.3610	Valid			
	4	0.890	0.3610	Valid			
	5	0.914	0.3610	Valid			

Source: Data Processed by Researchers, 2025 (SPSS 26)

The results of the validity test in table 2 show that all statement items in the HR variables (X1), Organizational Culture (X2), Job Satisfaction (Y), and Service Quality (Z) have a validity coefficient value of > 0.3610, so they are declared valid. The results of the reliability test show that the Cronbach's Alpha value for the HR variables (0.888), Organizational Culture (0.851), Service Quality (0.837), and Job Satisfaction (0.925) is > 0.700, so all instruments are declared reliable.

Classical Assumption Test

**Table 3. Normality Test
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test**

	Unstandardized Residual
N	103
Test Statistics	.041
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.200c

- a. Test distribution is Normal.
- b. Calculated from data.
- c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.

Source: Data Processed by Researchers, 2025 (SPSS 26)

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Table 4. Heteroscedasticity Test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1,797	1,692		1,062	.291
	X1	-.016	.102	-.017	-.158	.874
	X2	.072	.070	.107	1,022	.309

a. Dependent Variable: abs_RES4

Source: Data Processed by Researchers, 2025 (SPSS 26)

The results of the normality test with Kolmogorov-Smirnov in table 3. show a residual significance value of $0.200 > 0.05$, which means the data is normally distributed. The heteroscedasticity test with the Glejser method in table 4. shows the significance value of variables X1 (0.874) and X2 (0.309) > 0.05 , so there is no heteroscedasticity. The multicollinearity test shows a Tolerance value (0.895) > 0.10 and VIF (1.117) < 10 , so there is no multicollinearity. The autocorrelation test with Durbin-Watson produces a value of 2.142 which is in the range of $dU (1.7603) < DW < 4-dU (2.2397)$, so there is no autocorrelation.

Path Analysis Results

Path analysis was conducted to test the direct and indirect influences between variables. The following is a summary of the path analysis results:

Table 5. Summary of Path Analysis Results

Path of Influence	Beta Coefficient	t value	Significance	Information
Sub-Structure 1 (Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction)				
HR (X1) → Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.195	2,038	0.044	Significant
Organizational Culture (X2) → Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.314	3,276	0.001	Significant
F test		F = 10.722	0,000	Significant
R Square (X1,X2 → Y)	0.177			
Sub-Structure 2 (Dependent Variable: Service Quality)				
HR (X1) → Service Quality (Z)	0.204	2,088	0.039	Significant
Organizational Culture (X2) → Service Quality (Z)	0.261	2,671	0.009	Significant
F test		F = 8.434	0,000	Significant
R Square (X1,X2 → Z)	0.144			
Sub-Structure 3 (Dependent Variable: Service Quality)				
Job Satisfaction (Y) → Service Quality (Z)	0.727	10,639	0,000	Significant
R Square (Y → Z)	0.528			
Indirect Influence (Mediation)				
HR (X1) → Y → Z	0.142	Sobel test = 0.317 0.9996		Not Significant
Organizational Culture (X2) → Y → Z	0.228	Sobel test = 0.196 1.2932		Not Significant

Source: Processed Data, 2025

Based on Table 5, all hypotheses testing the direct influence (H1, H2, H3, H4, H5) were accepted. Human resources and organizational culture were proven to have a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction. Similarly, human resources, organizational culture, and job satisfaction had a positive and significant influence on service quality. The F-test results showed that human resources and organizational culture simultaneously had a significant influence on job satisfaction (H6 was accepted) and service quality.

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The coefficient of determination (R^2) value shows that human resources and organizational culture simultaneously explain 17.7% of the variation in job satisfaction (Y) and 14.4% of the variation in service quality (Z). Job satisfaction alone is able to explain 52.8% of the variation in service quality, indicating a strong influence. However, the results of the mediation test using the Sobel test showed that the indirect effect of HR on service quality through job satisfaction (H7) and the indirect effect of organizational culture on service quality through job satisfaction (H8) were not significant ($p > 0.05$). Thus, hypotheses H7 and H8 were rejected, meaning job satisfaction was not proven to be a significant mediator in this research model.

Discussion

The Influence of HR on Job Satisfaction

The research results prove that HR has a positive and significant influence on employee job satisfaction. This finding aligns with research (Syahputra et al., 2023) This demonstrates that high-quality human resources can provide positive experiences and increase satisfaction. Employees who possess competencies that meet job demands tend to feel more confident, comfortable, and satisfied because they are able to achieve work targets. This confirms the Human Capital theory that investing in improving human resource competencies and skills will benefit not only the organization but also the individual in the form of job satisfaction.

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction

Organizational culture has been shown to have a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction, with a larger beta coefficient (0.314) than human resources. This finding strengthens the research findings. (Wahyutomo & Zikri, 2024) which states that a strong organizational culture, such as teamwork, open communication, and commitment to company values, can increase employee job satisfaction. An organizational culture that values engagement, supports innovation, and emphasizes integrity creates a positive and conducive work environment. This fosters employee internal motivation and a sense of appreciation, which ultimately increases job satisfaction.

The Influence of Human Resources on Service Quality

This study also proves that human resources have a positive and significant influence on service quality. This result is consistent with the findings of (Lufitasari et al., 2023) And (Sahriani et al., 2022) which states that human resource quality is a key factor in achieving optimal public services. Competent, highly motivated, and continuously developing human resources through training will be able to provide responsive, accurate, and professional services. Strong technical and soft skills enable employees to effectively implement PTSP procedures and meet public needs.

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Service Quality

Organizational culture has been shown to have a positive and significant influence on service quality. This finding supports research. (Tui et al., 2024) And (Rusdi, 2023) This demonstrates that a positive organizational culture contributes significantly to improving the quality of public services. Values such as service orientation, work ethic, and integrity, deeply embedded within the organization, are reflected in employees' daily behavior. A culture that encourages innovation and collaboration enables organizations to continuously adapt to change and improve service processes.

The Influence of Job Satisfaction on Service Quality

Job satisfaction has a very strong and significant influence on service quality, with a beta coefficient of 0.727. This indicates that employees who are satisfied with their jobs tend to provide significantly better service. This finding aligns with research. (Syahputra et al., 2023) And (Wahyutomo & Zikri, 2024) which emphasizes that job satisfaction is a key driver of performance and service quality. Employees who feel valued, have good relationships with their coworkers, and receive fair compensation will have a high level of enthusiasm and commitment to providing the best for the community.

The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction

Although all direct effects were significant, this study found that job satisfaction did not act as a significant mediator in the relationship between human resources and organizational culture on service quality. The Sobel test results for both mediation pathways showed a p -value > 0.05 . This indicates that at the Bandung High Court, the influence of human resources and organizational culture on service quality is predominantly direct, without prior improvement in job satisfaction.

This finding provides a new perspective that is different from several previous studies, such as (Emria & Nurhidayati, 2025) which found a significant mediation effect. Several factors may explain this result. First, the context of public organizations, particularly judicial institutions, may have distinct characteristics. The routine nature of public service tasks and strict procedures may make competency and work culture (external factors) more directly

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impact output quality, while job satisfaction (internal factors) plays a more direct role as a consequence of working conditions, rather than a primary prerequisite for quality service. Second, descriptive results indicate that despite high job satisfaction, compensation and promotion indicators are rated low. This may indicate that employees continue to provide excellent service due to their professionalism and task demands, despite unsatisfying aspects of their work. In other words, strong professional norms and organizational culture may be key drivers of service behavior, surpassing individual feelings of satisfaction.

The theoretical implication of these findings is the importance of considering organizational context and characteristics when testing mediation models. In organizations with strong professional cultures and norms, psychological variables such as job satisfaction may not always be the mechanism linking organizational factors to performance. Practically, for the Bandung High Court, these results confirm that efforts to improve service quality can be focused on directly strengthening human resource competencies through training and development, as well as cultivating organizational values that support excellent service, while continuing to strive to increase job satisfaction as a goal that is beneficial for employee well-being.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that human resources and organizational culture directly play a significant role in improving the quality of the One-Stop Integrated Service at the Bandung High Court. Organizational culture was shown to have a more dominant influence than human resources on service quality. Job satisfaction was also shown to be a very strong predictor of service quality. However, contrary to the initial hypothesis, job satisfaction was not shown to mediate the influence of human resources and organizational culture on service quality. This indicates that in the judicial environment, the influence of organizational factors on service quality is more direct.

These findings imply that improving service quality in judicial institutions needs to focus on directly strengthening human resource capacity through relevant and sustainable training programs, as well as strengthening an organizational culture that emphasizes the values of integrity, service orientation, and innovation. Although job satisfaction does not mediate, efforts to improve it remain important as an organizational goal in creating a positive work environment. Future research is recommended to explore other mediating variables such as organizational commitment or employee engagement, as well as conduct comparative studies across various public service institutions to deepen our understanding of the dynamics of the relationships between these variables.

REFERENCES

- Alivia, P., & Raharjo, TH (2024). The Influence of Human Resource Competence, Work Motivation, and Job Satisfaction on the Service Quality of District Office Employees in Semarang City. *BAEJ: Business and Accounting Education Journal*, 5(2), 149–169. <https://doi.org/10.15294/baej.v5i2.10464>
- El-sayed, M., Wahba, M., Ragheb, M.A., & Elgharabawy, A. (2021). The Impact of Job Commitment on the Relationship between Organizational Culture and Sustainable Development. 8, 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1106998>
- Emria, H., & Nurhidayati. (2025). The Role of Human Resources (HR) Competence and Organizational Culture on Service Quality in Improving Employee Performance at Pertamina Central Hospital, Jakarta. *SAMaj: Sultan Agung Management Journal*, 2(3), 206–219.
- Erlinda. (2025). Policy for Improving the Quality of One-Stop Integrated Services (PTSP) at the Ministry of Religion Office, Purbalingga Regency. *Gema Perencana Scientific Journal*, 3(3), 447–464.
- Esisuarni, Alqadri, H., & Nellitawati. (2024). The Importance of Work Motivation in Improving Employee Performance. *Niara Journal*, 17(2 SE-Articles), 478–488. <https://doi.org/10.31849/niara.v17i2.23149>
- Feri, S., Rahmat, A., & Supeno, B. (2020). The Influence of Motivation, Transformational Leadership Style, and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance Through Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable in a Study at PT. Champion Kurnia Djaja Technologies. *INOBIIS: Indonesian Journal of Business and Management Innovation*, 4(1 SE-), 134–151. <https://doi.org/10.31842/jurnalinobis.v4i1.172>
- Firlana, H. (2025). The Impact of Digital Transformation on Human Resource Management in the Indonesian Public Sector. *TEMATICS: Technology Management and Informatics Research Journals*, 7(1 SE-Articles), 49–59. <https://doi.org/10.52617/tematics.v7i1.714>
- Ghaleb, BDS (2024). The importance of organizational culture for business success. *Journal of Multidisciplinary*

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- Research and Technological Innovation, 2(03 SE-Articles), 727–735. <https://doi.org/10.59653/jimat.v2i03.1098>
- Guruh Suksmono Aji, & Iva Khoiril Mala. (2024). Improving Human Resources Quality to Achieve Competitive Advantage in the Digital Era: Trends, Innovations, and Challenges. *Journal of Management and Creative Economy*, 2(3 SE-Articles), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.59024/jumek.v2i3.357>
- Hendri Gusma Hendra, Dori Mittra Candana, & M. Afuan. (2024). The Influence of Organizational Culture and Work Environment on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at PT. Padang Distribusindo Raya DC Padang Aro. *EBISMAN EBusiness Management*, 2(3 SE-Articles), 80–96. <https://doi.org/10.59603/ebisman.v2i3.520>
- Ilhami, I., Fajri, A., Maharani, AD, Asihani, A., Yudistira, A., Septiwi, I., Ramadhani, N., Salsabilah, R., Alvia, R., Iglana, R., Safitri, RN, Baladah, SS, & Putri, TD (2024). Mapping the Concept of Service Culture, Excellent Service, and Customer Satisfaction: A Literature Review. *Journal of Education and Teaching Review*, 7(2 SE-Articles), 5374–5382. <https://doi.org/10.31004/jrpp.v7i2.28001>
- Lufitasari, S., Saepudin, A., & Kurniawati. (2023). Public Administration Study Program, Bandung College of Administrative Sciences. *Equilibrium: Scientific Journal of Economics, Management and Accounting*, 12(2), 151–157.
- Medah, MH, Man, S., Taolin, D., Niha, SS, & Yasinto, Y. (2024). The Influence of Motivation, Transfer, and Quality of Public Services on Employee Performance Through Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at the Population and Civil Registration Service of Kupang Regency. *Scientific Journal of Batanghari University, Jambi*, 24(3), 2726–2731. <https://doi.org/10.33087/jiubj.v24i3.5412>
- Mokoginta, C., Dua, IL, & Rumerung, J. (2023). Improving Service Quality for Public Satisfaction at the Manado State Administrative Court. *MABP Journal*, 5(April), 79–92.
- Mukmin, S., & Prasetyo, I. (2021). The Influence of Leadership Style and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance Through Employee Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable. *Journal of Business Management*, 4(2), 123–136. <https://doi.org/10.37504/jmb.v4i2.297>
- Rusdi. (2023). Quality Work Culture as a Standard of Quality Service. *AKADEMIC: Journal of Economics & Business Students*, 3(3), 166–175. <https://doi.org/10.37481/jmeb.v3i3.611>
- Sahriani, S., Razak, M., & Said, M. (2022). The Influence of Human Resources Quality, Organizational Culture, and Work Ethic on Public Services of Barru Regency Transportation Agency Employees. *Cendekia Akademika Indonesia (CAI)*, 1(1 SE-Articles), 43–52. <https://e-jurnal.nobel.ac.id/index.php/cai/article/view/3361>
- Shopiana. (2021). HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN EDUCATION. *ACIEM: Annual Conference On Islamic Education Management*, 442–448.
- Susanti, EN, Nasrul, HW, Octaria, M., Hakim, L., Ismanto, W., & Desfika, I. (2023). The Influence of Organizational Culture, Quality of Human Resources, Motivation, and Work Discipline on Employee Performance. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Business Management and Accounting (ICOBIMA)*, 2(1), 193–202.
- Syahputra, M., Zulkarnain Nasution, & Siti Lam'ah Nasution. (2023). The Influence of Human Resource Quality, Service Quality, and Instructor Performance on Student Satisfaction at the LKP Intermedia Training Center. *JEMSI (Journal of Economics, Management, and Accounting)*, 9(5 SE-Articles), 1704–1714. <https://doi.org/10.35870/jemsi.v9i5.1415>
- Taufiqurrohman Syahuri, & M. Reza Saputra. (2024). The Use of Technology in the Judicial Process and Its Impact on Access to Justice. *Amendment: Indonesian Journal of Defense, Politics, and Law*, 1(3 SE-Articles), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.62383/amandemen.v1i3.206>
- Tui, A.T., Tahir, A., & Isa, R. (2024). The Influence of Organizational Culture on the Quality of Public Services at the Motolohu Village Office, Randangan District. *Kybernology Journal of Government and Public Administration*, 2(2 SE-Articles), 480–490. <https://doi.org/10.71128/kybernology.v2i2.134>
- Wahyutomo, D., & Zikri, IFM (2024). Organizational Culture as an Influential Factor in Determining Employee Performance and Service Quality with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable. *Jurnal Minfo Polgan*, 13(1 SE-), 520–532. <https://doi.org/10.33395/jmp.v13i1.13708>
- Wirawan, DG, Baharuddin, M., & Tjenreng, Z. (2025). Implementation of Good Governance in Bureaucratic Reform to Improve Public Services in Indonesia. *Journal of PKM Business Management*, 5(1), 179–193. <https://doi.org/10.37481>
- Yani, A., Hakim, ML, Arifudin, & Azmi, ADN (2024). One-Stop Integrated Service (PTSP) Policy from a Good Governance Perspective (Study at the One-Stop Integrated Investment Service Office of Sukabumi Regency).

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AL-QISTH LAW REVIEW, 7(2), 215–237.

Zahwa Alia Putri, Silvia, S., Siti Nur Aisyah, Viola Nofrilia, Jumiati, J., & Boni Saputra. (2025). Bureaucratic Reform in the Quality of Public Services: A Literature Review. *Journal of Communication and Social Political Sciences*, 2(4 SE-Articles), 1011–1019. <https://doi.org/10.62379/jiksp.v2i4.2594>